

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Brief Review on Naegleria Fowleri-Brain Eating Amoeba

Jyoti Sadgir*, Sagar Dalvi

Dr. Naikwadi College of Pharmacy, Jamgaon Sinnar Dist-Nashik(MH) India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

N .Fowleri ,. Primary
amebic
meningoencephalitis,
Olfactory Nerve, CNS.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14469190

ABSTRACT

N. Fowleri causes destruction of neurons and explains why this is also known as the “brain-eating amoeba”. Naegleria fowleri is a free-living, thermophilic, pathogenic flagellate amoeba belonging to the Heterolobosea class. feeds predominantly on bacteria on living in natural bodies of warm freshwater, from where it has been frequently detected. Being a free-living protist, N. fowleri feeds mainly on bacteria, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative. PAM occurs significantly in immunologically strong individuals as well as in healthy children and young adults, having recent exposure to recreational freshwater. the entry of N. fowleri through nasal cavity when water is forced or splashed into the nose. PAM is characterized by similar signs and symptoms to those of viral or bacterial meningitis including fever, headache, stiff neck, vomiting, anorexia, seizures, ultimately death. symptoms that may vary from 2 to 3 days to up to as long as 7–15 days. This review will discuss the pathogenesis, Mode of transmission, life cycle, risk factor, diagnosis, treatment of N. fowleri infections in human.

INTRODUCTION

Naegleria fowleri is a free-living, thermophilic, pathogenic flagellate one-celled organism having a place with the Heterolobosea class. In hotter months of the year, N. fowleri multiplies as it can endure temperatures up to 45°C and takes care of transcendingly on microscopic organisms on residing in normal collections of warm freshwater, from where it has been regularly detected.[1,2] N. fowleri is otherwise called amphibolic one-celled organism and there are three morphological phases of

Naegleria species life cycle have been recognized: trophozoite (10-25 μm), pear-shaped transitory flagellate stage (10-16 μm) and blister stage (8-20 μm).[3,4] .Being a free-living protist, N. fowleri takes care of fundamentally on microscopic organisms, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative, as well as on green growth, and yeast. The reaction shown by N. fowleri to microorganisms is through the arrangement of food cups, chemotaxis and chemokines.[5,6] N. fowleri is the main species that causes a deadly

***Corresponding Author:** Jyoti Sadgir

Address: Dr. Naikwadi College of Pharmacy, Jamgaon Sinnar Dist-Nashik (MH) India.

Email ✉: sadgirjyoti70@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

cerebrum disease called essential amoebic meningoencephalitis (PAM), while more than 40 types of Naegleria have been recognized. However PAM is uncommon, it is a deadly human illness with a death pace of 95%-97%. [7,8] The passing happens inside roughly seven days, as it is a deadly, necrotizing, fulminant, and haemorrhagic meningoencephalitis. [9] PAM happens essentially in immunologically resilient people as well as in solid kids and youthful grown-ups, having ongoing openness to sporting freshwater. [10] PAM is a waterborne sickness, so most cases are related with plunging and swimming exercises in less chlorinated pools, dirtied trenches and spas or during relaxation sports, for example, waterskiing in defiled natural water sources, and the utilization of neti pots for nasalpurifying ablution. [11]

Brain Eating Amoeba

Microscopic view of Naegleria fowleri

This intense contamination is created by the section of *N. fowleri* through nasal cavity when water is constrained or sprinkled into the nose. *N. fowleri* causes obliteration of neurons and makes sense of why this is otherwise called the "brain-eating single adaptable cell"; this term shows that

the proteins and poisons of this parasite are regularly associated with the annihilation (eating-up) of the brain. [12,13] PAM is described by comparative signs and side effects to those of viral or bacterial meningitis including fever, migraine, firm neck, heaving, anorexia, seizures, at last passing commonly happens inside 3-7 days after the presence of these signs and symptoms. [14] The harmfulness of the strain and the size of the inoculum are engaged with deciding the time frame between starting contact with the pathogenic *N. fowleri* and the presence of clinical signs and side effects that might differ from 2 to 3 days to up to up to 7-15 days. [15]

Pathogenesis:-

N. fowleri has been remembered to taint the human body by entering the host through the nose when water is sprinkled or constrained into the nasal depression. Infectivity happens first through connection to the nasal mucosa, trailed by headway along the olfactory nerve and through the cribriform plate (which is more permeable in kids and youthful grown-ups) to arrive at the olfactory bulbs inside the CNS. [16] Once *N. fowleri* arrives at the olfactory bulbs, it gets a critical invulnerable reaction through initiation of the intrinsic resistant framework, including macrophages and neutrophils. [17] *N. fowleri* enters the human body in the trophozoite structure. Structures on the outer layer of trophozoites known as food cups empower the creature to ingest microscopic organisms, growths, and human tissue. [18] notwithstanding tissue annihilation by the food cup, the pathogenicity of *N. fowleri* is subject to the arrival of cytolytic particles, including corrosive hydrolases, phospholipases, neuraminidases, and phospholipolytic catalysts that assume apart in have cell and nerve destruction. [19]

Diagrammatic Representation of N. Fowleri Pathophysiology

The mix of the pathogenicity of *N. (20) fowleri* and the serious resistant reaction coming about because of its presence brings about critical nerve harm and ensuing CNS tissue harm, which frequently bring about death. From defiled water, *N. fowleri* entered the nose. (21) *N. fowleri* trophozoites move up to enter the mind, (22) Various amoebae are seen blended with the deteriorating neurones, glial cycles, and neutrophil polymorphs with significant fixations in the perivascular locales and in the lumina of veins (23). At the point when *N. fowleri* are hatched with have cells in vitro, have cells show cell shrinkage, cell harm, attack and annihilation by means of phagocytic cycles (24)

Mode Of Transmission :-

Naegleria fowleri taints individuals while water containing the single adaptable cell enters the body through the nose. This commonly happens when individuals swim or making a plunge warm freshwater places, similar to lakes and waterways. The *Naegleria fowleri* one-celled critter then, at that point, makes a trip up the nose to the cerebrum where it obliterates the mind tissue. (25)

This disease happens right off the bat by connection of one-celled critter to the nasal mucosa, which then, at that point, moves along the olfactory nerve and reaches the

olfactory bulbs through the cribriform plate inside the CNS.(26) Besides, there is plausible that the gamble of PAM is higher among those kids and youthful grown-ups that have more permeable cribriform plates.(27) Exploration has uncovered that disease can't be started by drinking debase water.(28)

Growth and life cycle :-

Naegleria feed on yeast, green growth and both Gram-negative and Gram-positive microbes (29). Food selectivity is seen with discoveries that filamentous cyanobacteria (e.g., *Anabaena*, *Cylindrospermum*, *Gloeotrichia*, and *Phormidium*) are eaten, while tight strings (*Oscillatoria*) and totals (*Aphanizomenon*) are not ingested. Unicellular *Chroococcaceae* (e.g., *Synechococcus*, *Aphanocapsa*, and *Microcystis*) are discharged later ingestion, showing that food choice happens inside food vacuoles. Ingestion relies upon the satiation status of the amoebae, as starved amoebae feed at higher rates contrasted and satisfied amoebae (29) Live microorganisms support ideal development contrasted and heat-killed microscopic organisms. Under these circumstances, the amoebae feed upon the microscopic organisms, and as development enters fixed stage and the food supply is spent, *N. fowleri* start to encyst. Growths, whenever held back from drying out, will stay feasible for a really long time, potentially years. (30) Throughout the phases of

leukocytes.). Nelson's development medium with fetal calf serum can be utilized to culture *Naegleria fowleri* (41) CSF stained with Giemsa-Wright stain to show the trophozoites while Gram-stain has no advantage uncovering the parasite (42). Clinical side effects additionally can be handed-off to analyze the contamination which included chill, fever, serious migraine, seizures, photophobia, cardiovascular anomalies, myocardial rot, and comma (43).

Treatment: -

Since the disease with *Naegleria fowleri* described by a high death rate and all data recorded are came from detailed cases so there isn't a lot of data in regards to treatment choices and should be refreshed through additional examinations and clinical preliminaries (44). As indicated by the examinations, Amphotericin B (AmB) is an enemy of contagious used to kill the parasite by instigating the apoptosis interaction (45). In any case, the greatest hindrance to treatment, is that most medications should be managed in high fixation to pass the blood- cerebrum boundary (BBB) and arrive at the base inhibitory focus (MIC) to kill the single adaptable cell. (46) PAM is a disease that happens when trophozoite, an infective phase of *N. fowleri* ready to attack the cerebrum which is related with warm water-related exercises. The pharmacodynamics of PAM found in the CNS is upset by the way that it requires a more drawn out investment for fundamental organization to enter and enter the objective organ. PAM is a disease that happens when trophozoite, an infective phase of *N. fowleri* ready to attack the cerebrum which is related with warm water- related exercises. The pharmacodynamics of PAM found in the CNS is upset by the way that it requires a more drawn out investment for fundamental organization to enter and enter the objective organ. Likewise, the introduction of the blood-cerebrum boundary makes it hard for the regulated medication to really

kill the parasite because of high selectivity making low medication entrance the objective tainted site in the CNS. (47) PAM is more vulnerable to solid people who are immunocompetent. PAM is a prompt reason for illness wherein passing might happen inside the space of days after side effects beginning.(48) Miltefosine is an enemy of malignant growth drug made to treat bosom disease and an antileishmanial drug that additionally gives promising in vitro treatment against *N. fowleri* and luckily, miltefosine has been Provided extraordinarily and generally by CDC as treatment of fulminant *Naegleria* contaminations (49).

REFERENCES

1. Yoder JS, Straif-Bourgeois S, Roy SL, et al. Primary amebic meningoencephalitis deaths associated with sinus irrigation using contaminated tap water. *Clinical Infectious Diseases.*, 2012; 55: 79-85.
2. Visvesvara GS, Moura H, Schuster FL. Pathogenic and opportunistic free-living amoebae: *Acanthamoeba* spp., *Balamuthia mandrillaris*, *Naegleria fowleri*, and *Sappinia diploidea*. *FEMS Immunology and Medical Microbiology*, 2007; 50: 1- 26.
3. Matin A. Primary amebic meningoencephalitis; a new emerging public health threat by *Naegleria fowleri* in Pakistan. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Drug Design*, 2017; 1: 1-3.
4. Trabelsi H, Dendana F, Sellami A, et al. Pathogenic free-living amoebae: epidemiology and clinical review. *Pathologie Biologie.*, 2012; 60: 399-405
5. Siddiqui R, Ali I, Cope JR, Khan NA. Biology and pathogenesis of *Naegleria fowleri*. *Acta Tropica*, 2016; 164: 375-394
6. De Jonckheere JF. Origin and evolution of the worldwide distributed pathogenic amoeboflagellate *Naegleria fowleri*. *Infection*

- Genetics and Evolution, 2011; 11: 1520-1528.
7. Baig AM, Khan NA. Novel chemotherapeutic strategies in the management of primary amoebic meningoencephalitis due to *Naegleria fowleri*. *CNS Neuroscience and Therapeutics.*, 2014; 20: 289-290.
 8. Mahmood K *Naegleria fowleri* in Pakistan-an emerging catastrophe. *Journal of College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan*, 2015; 25: 159-160.
 9. Heggie TW. Swimming with death: *Naegleria fowleri* infections in recreational waters. *Journal of Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease.*, 2010; 8: 201-206
 10. Gupta R, Parashar M, Kale A. Primary amoebic meningoencephalitis. *Journal of Association of Physicians of India*, 2015; 63: 69-71
 11. Matin A. Primary amoebic meningoencephalitis; a new emerging public health threat by *Naegleria fowleri* in Pakistan. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Drug Design.*, 2017; 1: 1-3
 12. Grace E, Asbill S, Virga K *Naegleria fowleri*: a review of the pathogenesis, diagnosis, and treatment options. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 2015; 59(11): 6677-6681.
 13. Baig AM. Pathogenesis of amoebic encephalitis: are the amoebae being credited to an „inside job“done by the host immune response? *Acta Tropica*, 2015; 148: 72-76. Yoder J, Eddy B, Visvesvara G, Capewell L, Beach M. The epidemiology of primary amoebic meningoencephalitis in the USA, 1962–2008. *Journal of Epidermology and Infection*, 2010; 138: 968- 975.
 14. Shariq A, Afridi FI, Farooqi BJ, Ahmed S, Hussain A. Fatal primary meningoencephalitis caused by *Naegleria fowleri*. *Journal of College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan.*, 2014; 24: 523-525.
 15. Jarolim KL, McCosh JK, Howard MJ, John DT. A light microscopy study of the migration of *Naegleria fowleri* from the nasal submucosa to the central nervous system during the early stage of primary amoebic meningoencephalitis in mice. *Journal of Parasitology*, 2000; 86: 50–55.
 16. John DT, Cole TB Jr, Bruner RA. 1985. Amebostomes of *Naegleria fowleri*. *Journal of Protozoology*, 1985; 32: 12–19
 17. Marciano-Cabral F, Cabral GA. The immune response to *Naegleria fowleri* amebae and pathogenesis of infection. *Journal of FEMS Immunology of Medical Microbiology*, 2007; 51: 243–259.
 18. De Jonckheere JF. Origin and evolution of the worldwide distributed pathogenic amoebic flagellate *Naegleria fowleri*. *Journal of Infection Genetic and Evolution*, 2011; 11: 1520-1528
 19. Yoder JS, Straif-Bourgeois S, Roy SL, Andreas j. Linscott. Primary amoebic meningoencephalitis deaths associated with sinus irrigation using contaminated tap water. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease.*, 2012; 55: 79-85.
 20. Visvesvara GS, Moura H, Schuster FL. Pathogenic and opportunistic free-living amoebae: *Acanthamoeba* spp., *Balamuthia mandrillaris*, *Naegleria fowleri*, and *Sappinia diploidea* *Journal of FEMS Immunology of Medical Microbiology*, 2007; 50: 1-26.
 21. Matin A. Primary amoebic meningoencephalitis; a new emerging public health threat by *Naegleria fowleri* in Pakistan. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Drug Design*, 2017; 1: 1-3.
 22. Schuster FL, Dunnebacke TH. Ultrastructural observations of experimental *Naegleria meningoencephalitis* in mice: intranuclear inclusions in amoebae and host cells *Journal of Protozoology* 1977; 24:489-497.

23. Visvesvara GS, Callaway CS.. Light and electron microscopic observations on the pathogenesis of *Naegleria fowleri* in mouse brain and tissue culture. *Journal of Protozoology* 1974 ; 21:239-250.
24. Cope JR, Murphy J, Kahler A, Gorbett DG, Ali I, Taylor B, Corbitt L, Roy S, Lee N, Roellig D, Brewer S, Hill VR, Primary Amebic Meningoencephalitis Associated With Rafting on an Artificial Whitewater River: Case Report and Environmental Investigation. *Clinical infectious diseases: an official publication of the Infectious Diseases Society of America*. 2018 ; 66: 548-553 .
25. Heggie TW. Swimming with death: *Naegleria fowleri* infections in recreational waters. *Journal of Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*. 2010;8:201-206.
26. Heggie TW, Küpper T. Surviving *Naegleria fowleri* infections: a successful case report and novel therapeutic approach. . *Journal of Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*. 2017;16:49-51
27. Shakeel S, Iffat W, Khan M. Pharmacy students' knowledge assessment of *Naegleria fowleri* infection. *Hindawi publishing corporation scientifica* 2016;2:16-22.
28. Anderson K, Jamieson A. 1974. Bacterial suspensions for the growth of *Naegleria* species. *Pathology* 1974; 6:79-84.
29. Xinyao L, Miao S, Yonghong L, Yin G, Zhongkai Z, Donghui W, Weizhong W, Chencai A. 2006. Feeding characteristics of an amoeba (Lobosea: *Naegleria*) grazing upon cyanobacteria: food selection, ingestion and digestion progress. *Journal of Microbial Ecology* 2006 ; 51:315-325.
30. Corff S, Yuyama S. 1976. Cessation of nuclear DNA synthesis in differentiating *Naegleria*. *Journal of Protozoology* 1976 ; 23:587-593.
31. González-Robles A, Cristóbal-Ramos AR, González-Lázaro M, Omaña-Molina M, Martínez-Palomo A. 2009. *Naegleria fowleri*: light and electron microscopy study of mitosis. *Experimental Parasitology* 2009 ; 122:212-217.
32. González-Robles A, Cristóbal-Ramos AR, González-Lázaro M, Omaña-Molina M, Martínez-Palomo A. 2009. *Naegleria fowleri*: light and electron microscopy study of mitosis. *Experimental Parasitology* 2009 ; 122:212-217.
33. Kao PM, Tung MC, Hsu BM, Hsueh CJ, Chiu YC, Chen NH, et al. Occurrence and Distribution . *Journal of applied microbiology* 2013 ; 50: 1-60.
34. Heggie TW & Küpper T. Surviving *Naegleria fowleri* Infections: A Successful Case Report and Novel Therapeutic Approach. *Journal of Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease* .2017;16 : 49–51.
35. Bellini NK, Santos TM, da Silva MTA, Thiemann OH. The Therapeutic Strategies Against *Naegleria fowleri*. *Journal of Experimental Parasitology* . 2018;187:1–11.
36. Majid MAA, Mahboob T, Mong BGJ, Jaturas N, Richard RL, Tian-Chye T, et al. Pathogenic Waterborne Free-Living Amoebae: An Update from Selected Southeast Asian Countries. *Journal of PLOS One*. 2017;12(2):1–17.
37. Farra A, Bekondi C, Tricou V, Mbecko JR, Talarmin A. Free-Living Amoebae Isolated in The Central African Republic: Epidemiological and Molecular Aspects. *The Pan African Medical Journal*. 2017;26:1–10.
38. Ithoi I, Lau YL, Fadzlan AA, Foad AI, Neilson RS, Nissapatorn V. Detection of Free Living Amoebae, *Acanthamoeba* and *Naegleria*, in Swimming Pools, Malaysia. *Tropical Biomedicine*. 2010;27(3):566–577.

39. Latiff NSA, Jali A, Azmi NA, Ithoi I, Sulaiman WYW, Yusuf N. The Occurrence of Acanthamoeba and Naegleria from Recreational Water of Selected Hot Springs in Selangor, Malaysia. *International Journal of Tropical Medicine*. 2018;13(3):21–24.
40. Shakeel S, Iffat W, Khan M. Pharmacy Students' Knowledge Assessment of Naegleria fowleri Infection. *Journal of Hindawi publishing corporation Scientifica (Cairo)*. 2016;2016:5–10.
41. Bellini NK, Santos TM, da Silva MTA, Thiemann OH. The therapeutic strategies against Naegleria fowleri. *Journal of Experimental Parasitology*. 2018;187:1-11
42. Siddiqui R, Ali IKM, Cope JR, Khan NA. Biology and pathogenesis of Naegleria fowleri. *Journal of Acta Tropica*. 2016;164:375-94
43. Visvesvara GS. Infections with free-living amebae. *Journal of Handbook of Clinical Neurology*. 2013;114:153-68.
44. Grace E, Asbill S, Virga K. Naegleria fowleri: pathogenesis, diagnosis, and treatment options. *Journals of Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*. 2015;59(11):6677-81.
45. Pugh JJ, Levy RA. Naegleria fowleri: Diagnosis, Pathophysiology of Brain Inflammation, and Antimicrobial Treatments. *Journal of ACS Chemical Neuroscience*. 2016;7(9):1178-9.
46. Cárdenas-Zúñiga R, Silva-Olivares A, Villalba-Magdaleno JA, Sánchez-Monroy V, Serrano-Luna J, Shibayama M. Amphotericin B induces apoptosis-like programmed cell death in Naegleria fowleri and Naegleria gruberi. *Journal of Microbiology*. 2017;163(7):940-9.
47. Rajendran K, Anwar A, Khan NA, Siddiqui R. Brain-Eating Amoebae: Silver Nanoparticle Conjugation Enhanced Efficacy of Anti-Amoebic Drugs against Naegleria fowleri. *Journal of ACS Chemical Neuroscience*. 2017;8(12):2626-30.
48. Tiewcharoen S, Rabablert J, Atitthep T, Katzenmeier G, Chetanachan P, Junnu V. Ultra Structure Changes of Diosgenin-Treated Human Monocyte U937-Derived Macrophages Induced by Naegleria fowleri Lysate. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*. 2017;48(5):945–954.
49. Cope JR, Conrad DA, Cohen N, Cotilla M, DaSilva A, Jackson J, et al. Use of The Novel Therapeutic Agent Miltefosine for The Treatment of Primary Amebic Meningoencephalitis: Report of One Fatal and One Surviving Case. *Journal of Clinical Infectious Disease*. 2016;62(6):774-776.

HOW TO CITE: Jyoti Sadgir*, Sagar Dalvi, A Brief Review on Naegleria Fowleri-Brain Eating Amoeba, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 2062-2069. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14469190>

